

THE EFFECT OF MATRIX PROPERTIES ON REINFORCEMENT
IN SHORT ALUMINA-FIBRE/ALUMINIUM METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of alloy matrix properties on room and high temperature strengthening in δ -Alumina reinforced Aluminium alloys has been investigated. It is shown that a simple 'rule of mixtures' strength analysis modified to account for the discontinuous and random orientation of the reinforcement can adequately explain these responses. Lack of room-temperature reinforcement in these systems occurs when the matrix properties result in a high value for V_{CRIT} . However by careful selection of the matrix alloy V_{CRIT} can be reduced, giving significant reinforcement of room-temperature strength. The elevated temperature reinforcement behaviour can be explained by the effect of temperature on the matrix properties. As temperature increases, V_{CRIT} for the composite decreases, producing the observed increased reinforcement at elevated temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years considerable interest has been shown in the reinforcement of Aluminium alloys by short δ -Alumina fibres [1]. Work has shown that these composites exhibit good interfacial bonding and improvements in room temperature modulus, and high-temperature modulus and strength [2]. However in the volume fractions investigated experimentally, these systems exhibit a number of anomalies in their reinforcement behaviour. A feature of many of the alloy/fibre combinations investigated is little or no improvement in room temperature strength despite obvious improvements in modulus. This

behaviour has been observed in a number of alloys reinforced by δ -Alumina fibres, in particular Al-Si alloys [1,2]. Equally as strange is that in other alloys containing similar volume fractions of reinforcement, considerable improvements in room-temperature strength are observed [3].

Another interesting phenomenon is the high-temperature response of these composites. It is clear from previous work [2] that these composites often exhibit room-temperature strengths below that of the unreinforced matrix alloy, but as their temperatures are raised they exhibit strengths considerably higher than the unreinforced matrix. Such data is interesting since it implies that the composites exhibit no reinforcement in strength at room-temperature, but as the test temperature is increased they begin to exhibit more extensive reinforcement. Such data also shows that the onset of this phenomenon occurs at a critical temperature which decreases as the volume fraction of reinforcement increases.

Dinwoodie et al [2] have discussed ways in which the room-temperature strength can be empirically optimised, however little work has been conducted to ascertain the fundamental reasons for this anomalous room and high-temperature reinforcement behaviour. This paper presents the results of such an investigation with an analysis of the matrix properties which affect reinforcement.

STRENGTH IN RANDOM SHORT-FIBRE REINFORCED MMC

An earlier paper [4] described a simple 'Rule of Mixtures' (ROM) analysis of strength in short-fibre reinforced metal matrix composites (MMC). The central feature of this analysis was a ROM equation modified to account for the lack of reinforcing efficiency due to (a) the discontinuous nature of the reinforcing fibres, and (b) the 3-D random orientation of the reinforcement. The strength of these composites was then given by:-

$$\sigma_c = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{uf} V_f \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{l}\right) + c^* \sigma_m^* (1 - V_f) \quad \dots (1)$$

where:-

- σ_c is the composite strength
- σ_{uf} is the strength of the reinforcing fibre
- V_f is the fibre volume fraction
- l_c is the critical transfer length
- l is the fibre length
- c^* is an empirical constant
- σ_m^* is the matrix flow stress at the fibre failure strain

This ROM analysis was based on the assumption that the fibres did not fracture until a unique stress-level (σ_{uf}) was reached, where they all fractured together. This was clearly an oversimplification for these randomly oriented Alumina fibres which have a distribution of fibre

strengths and which exhibit a distribution of fibre stresses due to their random 3-D orientation. The resulting equation does however allow some analysis of the anomalous reinforcement behaviour of these composites.

The ROM diagrams (strength/ V_f) for these composites can be calculated using equation (1) and a consideration of the decrease in residual matrix strength with increasing fibre volume fraction, ie

$$\sigma = \sigma_{Um} (1 - V_f) \quad \dots (2)$$

where:-

σ is the residual matrix strength
 σ_{Um} is the unreinforced matrix strength

The effect of matrix alloy or temperature on composite strength can therefore be established if values for the variables σ_{Uf} , σ_m^* , σ_{Um} , l , l_c and c^* are known, and their temperature dependence evaluated.

CALCULATION OF THE REINFORCEMENT BEHAVIOUR IN SHORT δ -ALUMINA REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOYS

Tables 1 and 2 contain the data required for the calculation of the ROM diagrams for some random short-fibre composites. Table 1 contains the results of room-temperature tensile tests on three unreinforced matrix alloys and table 2 typical properties of short δ -Alumina fibres (Saffil) [5]. Using this data all the variables in equations 1 and 2 can be evaluated, except c^* which has been shown previously [4] to lie between 1 and 2 for these alloys. Figure 1 shows the resulting calculated ROM diagrams which are compared with the experimentally determined strengths of 0.25 V_f composites manufactured by the preform and pressure infiltration route [4]. These diagrams show that good agreement can be obtained between this simple ROM formalism and the experimentally determined strengths. They also allow some analysis of the underlying reasons for the anomalous reinforcement behaviour in short δ -Alumina fibre-reinforced Aluminium alloys.

TABLE 1
Average Tensile Data for Unreinforced and Reinforced Alloys

	U.T.S.(MPs)	σ_m^* (MPa)	c^*
Unreinforced Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg	273	226	-
0.25 V_f Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg	266	-	1
Unreinforced Al-12Si	143	88	-
0.25 V_f Al-12Si	165	-	1
Unreinforced Al	55	50	-
0.25 V_f Al	178	-	2

TABLE 2
Typical Properties of Saffil Fibre 4 [5]

Composition - 96-97% Al ₂ O ₃	Crystal Structure δ-Alumina
Mean Diameter - 3µm	Elastic Modulus 300 GPa
Strength - 2000 MPa	Failure Strain 0.67%
Fibre length 500µm	

Room Temperature Strength

It is clear from the tensile data in table 1 that these composites exhibit significantly different reinforcement behaviour at room temperature. In the case of the Al-Zn-Mg and Al-Si alloys the 0.25V_f of short-fibre results in little or no reinforcement. In the Al-Zn-Mg matrix there is a 3% reduction in strength compared with the unreinforced alloy, and in the Al-Si matrix a 15% improvement in room-temperature strength. The second type of behaviour is exhibited by the commercially pure Aluminium matrix which shows an increase in strength by more than 300% on the addition of a 0.25V_f of Saffil fibre. This difference in reinforcement behaviour is easily rationalised if one compares the ROM strength diagrams in fig.1.

Figure 1 shows the ROM diagrams for composites based on these three Aluminium alloy matrices. Superimposed on these diagrams are the typical volume fraction ranges investigated experimentally using the preform and pressure infiltration technique (0.15-0.30 V_f). If this V_f range is compared with the strengthening behaviour it is clear why these systems exhibit two significantly different reinforcement behaviours.

ROM diagrams show two important volume fraction parameters (i) V_{MIN} - the critical volume fraction at which the failure of the composite changes from a multiple fibre fracture mode to instantaneous failure of the composites, and (ii) V_{CRIT} - the volume fraction which must be exceeded to produce reinforcement of strength above that of the unreinforced alloy. It is clear from fig.1 that V_{CRIT} varies for the different composites and it is this variation which results in the significantly different room-temperature reinforcement behaviour.

Considering the Al-Zn-Mg and Al-Si - based composites it is clear that the commonly investigated V_f ranges lie in the region of V_{MIN} and V_{CRIT}. The amount of reinforcement of room-temperature strength is therefore small. In the case of the Al-Zn-Mg alloy the commonly investigated V_f range lies below V_{CRIT}. Composites produced using this alloy would therefore exhibit strengths below that of the unreinforced matrix. In the case of the Al-Si alloy some higher V_f composites exceed V_{CRIT}, however the reinforcement in such composites is small due to the low volume-fraction dependence of strength in pseudo-random short-fibre composites.

The behaviour in commercially pure Aluminium matrix composites however is significantly different. This system exhibits a low value for V_{CRIT}

Figure 1(a) ROM diagram for δ -Alumina fibre-reinforced Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg composites

Figure 1(b) ROM diagram for δ -Alumina fibre-reinforced Al-12Si composites.

Figure 1(c) ROM diagram for δ -Alumina fibre-reinforced Aluminium Composites

which accounts for the significant reinforcement of room-temperature strength observed in these composites.

The critical parameter to assess the level of reinforcement at a given volume-fraction of fibre is therefore V_{CRIT} . If V_{CRIT} is small the experimentally accessible volume fractions will have $V_f > V_{CRIT}$ and therefore exhibit reinforcement of room-temperature strength. At V_{CRIT} $\sigma_c = \sigma_{um}$, therefore rearranging equation (1) gives:

$$V_{CRIT} = \frac{(\sigma_{um} - \sigma_m^*)}{\frac{1}{2} \sigma_{uf} V_f (1 - \frac{1}{21}) - \sigma_m^*} \quad \dots (3)$$

This indicates that V_{CRIT} is highly dependent on the properties of the matrix alloy. It is clear from equation (3) that V_{CRIT} depends primarily on the value of σ_m^* and the stress-difference $(\sigma_{um} - \sigma_m^*)$. If σ_m^* is increased (for a constant σ_{um}) or if both σ_{um} and σ_m^* change such that the difference $(\sigma_{um} - \sigma_m^*)$ decreases, then V_{CRIT} is reduced to lower reinforcement volume fractions. This shows that matrix alloys which exhibit reinforcement at room-temperature will be those with a small value for the stress-difference $(\sigma_{um} - \sigma_m^*)$, typically alloys which exhibit a small difference between their yield stress and UTS, ie alloys which have a low rate of workhardening. This behaviour is confirmed experimentally by the data in table 1 which shows that the 0.25V_f composite which exhibits extensive reinforcement of room-temperature strength is that based on a commercially pure Aluminium matrix which exhibits an extremely low value for $(\sigma_{um} - \sigma_m^*)$ due to the alloy's low rate of workhardening. Thus the room-temperature reinforcement of short δ -Alumina reinforced Aluminium alloys is highly dependent on the matrix alloy employed and can be optimised by the use of a matrix which exhibits a low rate of workhardening.

High-Temperature Strength

The anomalous high-temperature strength of short Alumina-fibre reinforced Aluminium alloys has been described above. Essentially a composite which exhibits no reinforcement of room-temperature strength can be made to exhibit considerable improvement in strength by simply heating it above a critical temperature. The increase in temperature must therefore be significantly altering the properties of the component phases such that there is a fundamental change in the micromechanical mechanisms responsible for reinforcement. Since equation (1) appears to adequately describe the room-temperature reinforcement behaviour of these composites it is important to identify the effect of temperature on the terms in this equation and how they modify the reinforcement behaviour at higher temperatures.

If one analyses the effect of temperature on the reinforcing fibres it is clear that the temperature excursions commonly employed (typically in the range 100-400°C) have little effect on the fibre properties. Therefore the term σ_{uf} in equation (1) can be assumed to be constant

during the elevated temperature excursions produced in these composites, if one considers the effect of temperature on the matrix properties however, it is clear that temperature excursions in the range 100-400°C have a significant effect on the matrix properties. As temperature increases the matrix strength decreases and the matrix strength terms σ_{um} and σ_m^* must therefore decrease with increasing temperature and the critical transfer length l_c must increase (since it is inversely related to the matrix yield strength). The high-temperature strength behaviour must therefore be controlled by the response of the matrix alloy to temperature. It should therefore be possible to describe the high temperature reinforcement behaviour of these composites using the formalism described above, as long as the temperature dependence of the matrix properties are evaluated.

Figure 2 shows typical data of this type for the temperature dependence of σ_{um} and σ_m^* in an unreinforced Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg alloy, and fig.3 shows the calculated high temperature strength behaviour of a series of composites based on this alloy. The results of such a calculation compare well with experimental data for a 0.25V_f δ -Alumina reinforced Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg composite produced by the preform and pressure infiltration route,

Figure 2 - The effect of temperature on the mechanical properties of Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg

Figure 3 - Comparison of the experimental and calculated high temperature strengths of Alumina reinforced Al-Zn-Mg composites (● experimental)

and appears to accurately recreate the important features of the high temperature reinforcement behaviour, ie (i) lack of reinforcement at room-temperature and a gradual development of reinforcement at higher temperatures, and (ii) a volume fraction dependence of the critical temperature of reinforcement. Since this simple model appears to accurately reflect the strengthening behaviour of these composites at elevated temperatures, it can be used to generate strength/volume - fraction/temperature data which can be interrogated to analyse the underlying reasons for the observed high-temperature strengthening behaviour.

Results above have show that the observed lack of room-temperature reinforcement in these composites results from matrix properties which give rise to relatively large values for V_{CRIT} . This is illustrated in fig.1(a) where the ROM diagram for the room-temperature strength of Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg - based composites is compared with the typical experimentally accessible V_f range. It is clear that the lack of reinforcement results from the fact that this volume-fraction range lies below V_{CRIT} . However, results have also shown that if the stress-difference $\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$ can be reduced, significant reinforcement of room-temperature strength can be observed. A similar mechanism appears to be the key to explanation of the high-temperature behaviour of these composites.

Figure 2 shows the effect of temperature on the properties of an unreinforced Al-Zn-Mg alloy. This shows that as well as decreasing the strength, increasing temperature also has a further significant effect. Figure 2 shows that as temperature increases the stress difference $\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$ decreases. Considering the formalism developed above this must have a significant effect on the reinforcement, equivalent to changing the matrix alloy to one with a smaller $(\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*)$. As temperature increases and $\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$ decreases, V_{CRIT} must therefore decrease. Thus at some critical temperature the composite will begin to exhibit a strength above the level of the unreinforced matrix alloy. This occurs when the composite volume fraction, V_f , exceeds V_{CRIT} at that particular temperature. The effect of temperature on the ROM diagrams for strength in δ -Alumina reinforced Al-4.0Zn-2.0Mg composites is shown in fig.4. This shows that as the test temperature is raised V_{CRIT} decreases significantly such that by 200°C all the composites in the volume-fraction range 0.15-0.30 are reinforcing the strength to levels significantly above that of the unreinforced matrix alloy.

The underlying reasons for the high-temperature strength behaviour of these composites can now be identified. As the temperature increases the matrix softens, and more significantly the stress-difference $\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$ and V_{CRIT} decrease. This means that at some critical temperature composite of volume fraction, V_f , will begin to reinforce the strength to levels above that of the unreinforced matrix strength (when $V_f > V_{CRIT}$). The temperature at which this onset of reinforcement occurs depends on the V_f of reinforcement and is shown in fig.5. This is relatively easy to understand since at room-temperature higher V_f composites are closer to V_{CRIT} and would therefore be expected to be the first composites to exceed V_{CRIT} as it decreases with increasing

Figure 4(a) ROM diagram for δ -Alumina fibre reinforced Al-Zn-Mg composites at 100°C

Figure 4(b) ROM diagram for δ -Alumina fibre - reinforced Al-Zn-Mg composites at 200°C

Figure 5 - Effect of volume fraction on the critical temperature for high-temperature reinforcement in δ -Alumina fibre reinforced Al-Zn-Mg composites.

temperature. As the test temperature exceeds the critical temperature the composites continue to exhibit increasing reinforcement as long as V_{CRIT} decreases. Eventually however, the composite strength becomes controlled by a balance between the slightly decreasing V_{CRIT} and a more significant softening of σ_{um} .

CONCLUSIONS

The room and high-temperature strength behaviour of pseudorandomly reinforced short-Alumina fibre/Aluminium alloy composites can be described by a simple ROM analysis. Such an analysis shows that the reinforcement behaviour of these composites is controlled primarily by the matrix properties, in particular the matrix's rate of workhardening. This controls the value of the stress difference ($\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$) and the resulting value of V_{CRIT} . The anomalous room-temperature reinforcement behaviour can therefore be simply explained in terms of (i) the effect of matrix alloy properties on the V_{CRIT} , and (ii) the magnitude of the composite volume-fraction relative to V_{CRIT} .

The anomalous high-temperature reinforcement can also be described using this simple formalism and can be explained by the effect of temperature on the matrix properties. Increasing the temperature results in a reduction in the stress-difference ($\sigma_{um}-\sigma_m^*$) of the matrix alloy and a decrease in V_{CRIT} . Such a decrease results in increasing amounts of reinforcement and a transition from little or no reinforcement at low-temperature to extensive reinforcement at higher temperatures.

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